

ORGANIZING THE CROP ROTATION SYSTEM**Adizov Sh.****Salimov Sh.****Rajabov A.**

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Placement of crop rotation fields. Based on the study of the experience of the CIS countries and the world in organizing crop rotation systems and field placement, we recommend placing vegetable, melon, and potato crops not as a separate array but within each farmer's holdings in the cotton-growing areas. Considering the labor-intensive care these crops require, the high yield per hectare, and the increased use of mineral and organic fertilizers for these lands, it is advised to place them closer to residential areas to reduce transportation costs.

After dividing the fields for gardens, vineyards, poplar groves, mulberry groves, and vegetable-melon-potato crops, the remaining lands will be allocated for the main crops such as cotton, wheat, and alfalfa. Due to the low fertility levels of the soil in the area, the possibility of obtaining high yields from agricultural crops is limited, and substantial amounts of mineral fertilizers per hectare are required to increase fertility. Alfalfa crops have been proven to increase soil fertility by 20-30% due to their ability to raise the natural nitrogen levels in the soil as a result of many years of research. Therefore, alongside cotton and wheat, we recommend planting perennial grasses (alfalfa) in 10% of the total cultivated area for each farmer's holdings.

This, in turn, will provide an additional source of fodder for the livestock owned by the farmers and the local population. We place agricultural crops such as cotton, wheat, alfalfa, vegetables, and melons, and their fields within the farmers' holdings for our developed land management project for the Al Bukhariy named area in the Vobkent district of the Bukhara region. The data on the placement of crops within the farmers' holdings are presented in Table 1 below.

According to the data, in comparison to the previous year, the changes in the area of cultivated lands according to the project are as follows: the area of cotton crops has decreased by 5.3%, the area for wheat cultivation has increased by 0.6%, the area for fodder crops has increased by 11.26%, and the area for food crops has increased by 3.84%.

After determining the types of land and the areas of agricultural crops according to the project, the value of the gross products obtained from them was identified.

Project No	Direction of agricultural production	Cultivated area	Including						
			cotton	wheat	alfalfa	corn	vegetables	poly crops	Potatoes
1	Farming, animal husbandry, horticulture, viticulture	133,5	45,5	30,4	37,3	6,9	6,7	4,0	2,7
2	Agriculture, horticulture, viticulture	128,8	69,6	46,4			6,4	3,8	2,6
3	Agriculture-horticulture	114	61,6	41,0			5,7	3,4	2,3
4	Agriculture, livestock, horticulture	124,2	41,9	27,9	35,3	6,6	6,2	3,7	2,5
5	Agriculture - viticulture	52,17	28,1	18,8			2,6	1,6	1
6	Agriculture and horticulture	83,36	45,0	30,0			4,1	2,5	1,6
7	Agriculture, livestock, horticulture	65,18	22,0	14,7	17,5	4,6	3,2	1,9	1,3
8	Agriculture-horticulture	60,82	32,9	21,9			3,04	1,8	1,2
9	Agriculture, livestock, horticulture	143,1	76,9	51,3			7,1	4,9	2,9
	total	905,05	423.6	282.4	90,1	18,1	45,04	27,6	18,1
	in %	100.0	46.8	31.2	9.96	2.0	4.98	3.06	2.00

Table 2

The value of the gross product produced under the project

No	Product type	Crop area, ha	Productivity, q/ha	product quantity, (ton)	price of 1 ton of product (thousand soums)	Gross product value (thousand soums)
1	2			3	4	5
1	Cotton	423,6	35	1482,6	90000	13343400

2.	Wheat Straw	282.4	50 20	1412,0 564,8	3000 150	4236000 84720
3.	Vegetables	45.04	200	900,8	4000	3603200
	Poly crops	27.6	260	717,6	5000	3588000
4.	Potatoes	18.1	180	325,8	6000	195480
5.	Slfalfa	90.1	180	291,92	250	72980
6.	Fruit	70.65	150	1059,75	10000	10597500
						982080
7.	Grapes	10.23	120	122,76	8000	
	Total for agriculture					36703360
8.	Milk			210	5000	1050000
9.	Meat			20	50000	1000000
10.	Cocoon			10.4	25000	260000
	Total livestock					2310000
	Total					39013360

After a thorough examination of the current state of the Al Bukhariy area, based on the existing 19 farms, 9 new farms were designed.

The transformation of land types within the designed farms from their current composition to the projected composition is carried out through land transformation – converting lands from one type to another. As a result, an area of 29.1 hectares, which was not being used in agriculture, is planned to be transformed. Of this, 11.48 hectares will be poplar-paulownia groves, 10.76 hectares mulberry groves, 0.42 hectares vineyards, 0.61 hectares orchards, and 3.88 hectares as plowed land.

Factors influencing the rationalization (optimization) of the sizes of the projected farm lands were studied, and a regression equation representing the relationship was formulated.

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